

GOVERNANCE TOWARDS AN OPEN WEB INDEX

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INTRODUCTION

A small number of dominant tech gatekeepers hold control over what can and cannot be found on the Web, which poses a threat to the transparent access to web information, resulting in a significant economic imbalance and a lack of information sovereignty for Europe.

The OpenWebSearch.eu project seeks to address this issue by constructing an Open Web Index Infrastructure, intended as a public good. Additionally, it aims to establish a cooperative ecosystem surrounding this infrastructure. [1] To ensure the sustainability of the Open Web Index beyond the project and to ensure transparency and accountability a tailor-made governance model is needed. It is necessary to establish clear roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes, as well as enable effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders.

The objective of the governance building task in the project is developing and piloting a model-governance framework for establishing, operating, scaling and sustaining an open search infrastructure at European scale. This includes governing the infrastructure, data assets, services and software.

The vision of the initiative is to make the core of the open web index a public good, available to everyone. This creates specific requirements for the governance as it should stay collaborative and independent from unbalanced influence. It should be ethical, open and create trust. Furthermore, it should be based in the EU. To enable a distributed network across Europe, the legal form of our organization needs to support decentralized decision-making and governance structures, allowing for participation from various stakeholders across different EU-countries.

METHODOLOGY

A Governance workshop was organized with participants from technical and non-technical domains to identify relevant stakeholders and comparable collaborative infrastructures as well as collect and discuss concerns related to the governance of an open web index. The results of the workshop were structured to a report and used as the starting point for the work.

Landscape Analysis

Already the project proposal identified some comparable organisations to be studied and analysed. In the workshop and other meetings this list of interesting and

relevant organisations was extended. Based on a pre-defined structure we collected information about these organisations, for example legal form, decision-making structures and funding models, to select the most relevant for further analysis and discussion. We took a closer look at some initiatives, such as European Open Science Cloud EOSC, EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure, GAIA-X, Copernicus programme and Galileo, to find out what we can learn from them.

Furthermore, we collected information about different funding sources and financial models including private and public as well as different combinations of the two. These have been further analysed and their pros and cons discussed and defined.

DISCUSSION

From this analysis we were able to identify possibilities, similarities and necessities for the governance framework as regards to their legal form, governing bodies and funding sources.

Based on the initial analysis we decided to study the following options further as the potentially suitable legal forms. The legal forms analysed are limited liability company, AISBL and EDIC. We are currently evaluating them and defining our requirements for the governance. The necessary governing bodies will depend on the legal form chosen. They will need to include strategic, executive, steering structures.

As the open web index aims to be a public service, special focus on the funding source and its independence is necessary. There will be a need for public funding, but also private funding and sales should be possible. The final funding model is likely to be a combination of different funding sources.

The next step will be to build and analyse alternative scenarios for different time frames and legal entities, based on the specific requirements of the project. Also taking into consideration that the final governance framework is dependent on political decisions.

REFERENCES

- [1] <https://openwebsearch.eu/>